

Revealing the Nature of Active Sites on Pt-Gd and Pt-Pr Alloys during the Oxygen Reduction Reaction

Regina M. Kluge,^{1,‡} Eleftherios Psaltis,^{1,‡} Richard W. Haid,¹ Shujin Hou,^{1,2} Thorsten O.

Schmidt,¹ Oliver Schneider,³ Batyr Garlyyev,^{,1} Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka^{*,1,2}*

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- 1 Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, James-Franck-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany.
- 2 Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany.
- 3 Institut für Informatik VI, Technische Universität München, Schleißheimerstraße 90a, 85748 Garching, Germany.

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Abstract: For industrial-scale applications of hydrogen fuel cells, the sluggish kinetics of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) has to be overcome. So far, only Pt-group catalysts show adequate performance and stability. A well-known approach to increase the efficiency and decrease the Pt loading is to alloy Pt with other metals. Still, for catalyst optimization, the nature of active sites is crucial. In this work, electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) was used to probe the ORR active areas on Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr in an acidic medium under reaction conditions. The technique detects localized fluctuations in the EC-STM signal, which indicate differences in the local activity. The *in-situ* experiments show that in contrast to pure Pt, terraces contribute the most to the overall activity, whereas sites with higher coordination, as found at the bottom of step edges or concavities, remain relatively inactive. These findings should be vital in designing nanostructured Pt-lanthanide electrocatalysts.

Introduction

The use of hydrogen as a fuel in proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) is attractive due to low operating temperatures, relatively high power density, and short start-up times.^{1,2,3} However, their widespread application requires improved PEMFC performance, which is mainly hindered by the sluggish kinetics at the cathode where the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) takes place.^{4,5,6,7} Consequently, suitable ORR catalysts offer optimal binding conditions to the reaction

intermediates.^{8,9,10} Today, state-of-the-art catalysts which show the best ORR performance and stability are based on platinum (Pt). However, Pt(111) binds key intermediates like *O ~0.2 eV and *OH ~0.1 eV too strongly, with * denoting an adsorption site on the surface.^{6,7,11} A possibility to improve the activity of Pt-based catalysts is to produce nanoparticles of particular shapes and sizes such that a maximum density of active centers at their surface is accessible to reactants and reaction intermediates. However, to develop efficient design strategies, the identification of the active sites is essential. In this regard, several experimental techniques have been developed, such as *in-situ* X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) to access the existing energy states of the active phase.¹² Alternatively, in scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM), a miniature electrochemical cell can assess the local reactivity.¹³ Another scanning probe technique, which benefits from an outstanding resolution, is electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM), in which structural changes or self-activation can be observed under reaction conditions.¹⁴ For further reading on active site identification, we recommend references 8,9,10,15,16,17.

Concerning the nature of active sites on pure Pt surfaces for the ORR, a geometric approach can link the binding energy of a particular site to its coordination: Highly coordinated sites bind reaction intermediates weaker than their undercoordinated counterparts.^{18,19} Such highly coordinated, and thus active sites, exist near the bottom of step edges or at concavities. Concerning the shape of ideal nanoparticles, it was concluded that concave nanoparticles should surpass the activity of Pt(111), whereas convex nanoparticles would show lower activities.²⁰ This identification of active sites is in line with spherical convex Pt nanoparticles performing worse than Pt(111) extended surfaces.^{21,22} By contrast, Pt nanoparticles with deliberately induced

concave defects²³ as well as nanoframes and –cubes with concave sites^{24,25} outperform extended Pt(111) surfaces. Thus, the identification of active sites and subsequent intelligent engineering of nanoparticles is a promising route in ORR catalysis.

A common strategy to reduce the Pt loading and increase the ORR performance is to alloy Pt with non-noble metals (*e.g.* transition metals or rare earth metals).^{26,27,28,29,30} Due to their negative heat of formation in comparison to transition metals, the rare-earth metal alloys have been stated to be potentially more stable.^{31,32,33} Indeed, alloying Pt with lanthanides such as lanthanum (La)^{34,35}, cerium (Ce)³⁵, praseodymium (Pr)^{36,37}, gadolinium (Gd)^{33,35,38,39,40,41} and others³⁵ leads to a superior ORR activity compared to pure Pt. When operating Pt alloy electrodes under ORR conditions, leaching of the surface solute metals and the formation of a Pt overlayer were reported.³¹ Moreover, in rare-earth Pt alloys, the compressive strain between the Pt overlayer and the alloyed core was stated to weaken the binding energies toward the ORR intermediates.^{35,40,42}

In this study, inspired by the structure-activity relations identified on pure Pt surfaces, we examined the nature of the ORR active spots on polycrystalline Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd surfaces. As a tool, EC-STM was used under reaction conditions. This technique can relate morphology to local reactivity *via* the noise level of the EC-STM signal (n-EC-STM).^{43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50} It is based on the idea that the tunneling barrier and its properties mainly govern the recorded signal and its stability. The tunneling barrier will experience spatial- and time-dependent changes by introducing a reaction at the electrode-electrolyte interface. These changes emerge as an increased noise level in the STM signal when the tip is placed over an active site compared to an inactive one. Using the n-EC-STM technique on Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr surfaces in an acidic medium, one can distinguish

surface areas of different activity levels. Sites with higher coordination, as found at the bottom of step edges or concavities, show the lowest noise level and thus the lowest activity. In contrast, terraces and sites with lower coordination located near the top of step edges show the highest contribution to the overall activity. This trend is different from the observations on pure Pt surfaces.^{18,20,43,47} A brief explanation for this kind of trend is that Pt(111) surfaces bind intermediates stronger than optimal^{6,7,11} while terraces of the Pt-lanthanide alloys tend to bind them too weak⁴². These findings can be used for the rational design of nanostructured ORR electrocatalysts based on Pt-lanthanide alloys. Guided by the n-EC-STM experimental results, one can predict that in contrast to pure Pt, “classical” round particles should outperform their concave counterparts for alloyed Pt-Gd and Pt-Pr nanostructures.

Experimental Methods

Polycrystalline Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd alloys (both Ø 5 mm, MaTecK, Germany) were investigated. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments were recorded in Ar-saturated (Argon 5.0, Westfalen, Germany) and O₂-saturated (Oxygen 4.5, Linde, Germany) diluted perchloric acid (0.1 M HClO₄, Suprapur, Merck, Germany) electrolyte at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. A mercury–mercurous sulfate electrode (MMS) (SI Analytics, Germany) and a polycrystalline Pt wire (99.9%, Goodfellow, Germany) were used as reference and counter electrodes, respectively. The electrode potential was converted to reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale *via* $U(\text{RHE}) = U(\text{MMS}) + 0.66 \text{ V} + 0.059 \text{ pH}$. For the polarization curves, a Pine Research Instrumentation rotator was used at 1600 rpm speed. Experiments were controlled by a VSP-300 potentiostat (BioLogic) and the EC-Lab® software (V11.30). The glassware was regularly cleaned with a 3:1 mixture of H₂SO₄ (96%, Roth) and H₂O₂ (30%, Roth), and subsequently rinsed with boiling, ultrapure water multiple times.

EC-STM was performed using a MultiMode EC-STM/EC-AFM (Veeco Instruments) connected to a Universal Bipotentiostat and a NanoScope III scan feedback controller. The STM tips were mechanically ripped from a Pt80Ir20 wire (GoodFellow, $\text{\O} 0.25 \text{ mm}$) and insulated with Apiezon wax.⁵¹ The homemade electrochemical cell consisted of the sample clamped between a stainless steel sample holder and a Teflon ring, which exposed a surface area of 0.126 cm^2 to the electrolyte. Pt wires (MaTecK, $\text{\O} = 0.5 \text{ mm}$, 99.99% purity) were employed as (quasi-) reference and counter electrodes. Note that due to the small geometry of the cell, conventional reference electrodes are impractical. However, the use of the Pt quasi-reference electrode has been proven reliable for n-EC-STM purposes.^{43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50} Measurements were performed at room temperature, and samples and electrolytes were exposed to air.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted with a SPECS XR50 X-ray source (SPECS GmbH) and a hemispherical energy analyzer PHOIBOS 150. The Al emission line at an energy of 1487 eV was imposed upon the sample. The data were fitted with the CasaXPS software. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were conducted on an X'Pert PRO PANanalytical instrument with a Ni-filtered Cu K_{α} radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The scanning step was $\sim 0.78^{\circ}$ per min, and a scanning region of $2\Theta = 10\text{--}87^{\circ}$ was applied for all samples.

Results

Before applying the n-EC-STM technique, CV and ORR activity measurements were performed on the Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd polycrystalline samples. Experimental details are given in the Experimental Methods. The CV measurements in 0.1 M HClO₄ are given in Figure S1 of the Supporting Material. The ORR activity was tested using a rotating disk electrode (RDE) set-up. The ORR polarization curves recorded during the anodic scan for the Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd samples are shown in

Figure 1, together with the polarization curve of pure Pt for comparison. In agreement with the literature,^{33,37} the following activity trend was observed at 0.9 V_{RHE}: Pt₅Gd > Pt₅Pr > Pt. Detailed electrochemical activity characterizations for Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr electrodes can be found in references 33 and 37, respectively. Besides the electrochemical characterization, XPS and XRD measurements were performed to assess the compositional and crystalline structure of both electrodes and are included in Figure S3 of the Supporting Information. Detailed reference XRD analysis of the Pt₅Pr electrode can be found in reference 37. The XRD measurement of the Pt₅Gd electrode is in accordance with its polycrystalline structure and also agrees well with the literature results.³⁵ As seen from Figure S3, the XPS signals of both lanthanides are rather low with respect to the Pt signals and indicate a de-alloyed surface. This is expected because both electrodes were exposed to potential cycling in acid before the XPS measurements, during which the lanthanides at the surface leached out until stable CVs were obtained.

Figure 1. Polarization curves (anodic sweeps) of the RDE experiments performed in O₂-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄ electrolytes with a scan rate of 50 mVs⁻¹ and a rotational speed of

1600 rpm. The polarization curves were iR-corrected. The activities of Pt₅Gd (orange) and Pt₅Pr (grey) are compared to polycrystalline Pt (black).

As a next step, n-EC-STM was employed to identify the active spots. A detailed introduction to the technique can be found in reference 43. A brief overview will be given in the following. The working principle is shown in **Figure 2**. In EC-STM, the sample potential can be controlled such that a reaction is either hindered (reaction “off”, **Figure 2a**) or enabled (“on”, **Figure 2b**). In the case of an ongoing reaction, the EC-STM signal over active areas is destabilized, which manifests itself as an increase in the noise level. The method holds for both STM modes, such that “EC-STM signal” means either tunneling current or tip-sample distance (height). In **Figure 2**, the spots near the top of the step edge are exemplarily assigned as active. Therefore, distinct spikes in the EC-STM signal are observed at the respective position in the height profile in the in-set of **Figure 2b**. This increase in the noise level during the EC-STM measurements serves as a means for the *in-situ* identification of active sites. In the past, n-EC-STM was employed for the investigations of various systems for the ORR, oxygen evolution reaction (OER), and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER).^{43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50} Already prior to the development of the n-EC-STM technique, it has been reported that the structure of the electrolyte (water) influences the tunneling barrier.^{52,53} The same was stated for the presence of ions near the solid-liquid interface.^{54,55} Therefore, it can be understood that continuous changes in the composition and structure of the tunneling medium will persistently modulate the tunneling barrier and thus the tunneling current. Such changes occur due to an ongoing reaction and are the most dominant at the site of the reaction. Therefore, the EC-STM signal at active sites is modulated by distinct spikes (noise features). The potentials for the reaction “on” and “off” conditions were chosen according to a linear potential sweep recorded in

the STM set-up. Typical curves of Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr are given in **Figure 2c** and Figure S2 in the Supporting Information, respectively. A potential of low or no current was chosen as the reaction “off,” and the electrode potentials with a notable increase in the ORR current were chosen as ORR “on”. The parameters for each n-EC-STM measurement are given in Table S1 of the Supporting Information.

Figure 2. a,b) The working principle of n-EC-STM used to identify the active sites. Sites of different coordination can be grouped according to the color code. Sites at the very bottom of the step edge (black) are unlikely to participate in the reaction due to steric hindrance.²⁰ The other types of sites are possible active sites. In the illustration, the sites near the top of the step edge (green) are exemplarily assigned as active. In the EC-STM measurement, the sample potential can be chosen such that a reaction is inhibited (a, “off”) or enabled (b, “on”). When a reaction is

ongoing, the EC-STM signal over the active areas is destabilized and shows a considerable increase in the noise level, which is locally confined to the active areas. In the example, this can be seen in the spikes in the EC-STM signal near the top of the step edge. Therefore, active sites can be identified *in situ*. Color code: oxygen (red), hydrogen (yellow), exposed tip atoms and sample atoms (silver), tip atoms isolated with wax (black), as indicated in the figure. c) Linear potential sweep of Pr₅Gd recorded in the EC-STM set-up (0.1 M HClO₄, exposed to air, scan rate 50 mVs⁻¹, recorded *versus* a Pt pseudo-reference electrode) to identify the sample potentials chosen for the reaction “on” and “off” conditions. The corresponding linear potential sweep of Pt₅Pr is given in Figure S2 of the Supporting Information.

In the following, n-EC-STM was applied to investigate both Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd. As already mentioned in the Introduction, sites of different coordination can be expected to possess different activities, and they can be distinguished *via* the noise level in the n-EC-STM measurements. The sites of different geometries present on the catalyst surface are indicated with different colors in **Figure 2**. Sites of “regular” coordination, such as terrace sites (colored in silver), sites with lower coordination, such as found at the top of step edges (green), and sites with higher coordination, as found at the bottom of step edges (blue), can be distinguished. The atoms at the very bottom of step edges (black) are unlikely to contribute to the reaction due to steric hindrances.²⁰ Note that **Figure 2** is a schematic illustration of the technique and the electrode surface. It is intended to show possible differences in coordination of various surface geometries.

At first, n-EC-STM was applied to Pt₅Gd in 0.1 M HClO₄. A typical image is given in **Figure 3**. During the image recording, the sample potential was switched from reaction “on” to “off”

conditions, as labeled in the image. The mapped area contains several step edges, two of which are marked in the picture with white dashed lines. When the reaction is turned “off”, the EC-STM permits imaging of the surface morphology with a stable signal. When the reaction is turned “on”, the imaging of the surface morphology is modulated by an increase in the noise level. The noise manifests itself as high-intensity spots in the EC-STM signal (bright dots) as seen in **Figure 3a**. From the noise level at a certain position or type of surface site, one can assess the local activity.⁴⁷ Already at first glance, the noise seems less present near the bottom of the step edges. This can be seen near the dotted lines or exemplarily also at the position marked with an arrow. In **Figure 3b**, a waterfall plot is shown, consisting of multiple line scans (height profile in scan direction) extracted from **Figure 3a** for the reaction “on” and “off” conditions. The line scans were performed across the two step edges marked in **Figure 3a**, and the position of the step edges is also marked in the waterfall plot. Again, it is apparent that the EC-STM signal bears more noise when the reaction is “on” than “off”. In the area of the step bottom, the noise level seems to be diminished compared to the rest of the surface when the reaction is ongoing. An exemplary position with a low noise level along the bottom of step edge no. 2 is marked by an arrow.

As a next step, the noise level is quantified with respect to the geometry of the surface areas. According to their different tentative coordination, they are divided into “terrace”, “step top” and “step bottom” (see also sketch in **Figure 2**). These sites possess the “regular”, a lower, and a higher coordination at the surface, respectively. In **Figure 3c**, the line scans for reaction “on” are stacked on top of each other. The data is divided into three sets. The data sets for step top and bottom are equal in size to make a profound comparison. The width of the step bottom and top sites are adjusted for each measurement individually and lie within a range of 3 to 7 nm. The necessity for

these variations is because of the dissimilar width of the investigated features. Besides, due to thermal drift and the shape of the tip, topographic features may be broadened.⁵⁶ Therefore, it may be required to take a wider range in data than two rows per feature (as idealized in **Figure 2**). The chosen data for **Figure 3c** is indicated in the figure. The quantification of the noise level will be explained in the following.

Figure 3. n-EC-STM measurements on Pt₅Gd in 0.1 M HClO₄. a) During the recording of the EC-STM image, the sample potential was varied from reaction “on” to “off” conditions, as labeled in the image. Multiple step edges are present, of which two are numbered and marked by a white dashed line. When the reaction is turned “on”, the surface morphology is mapped with a

considerable noise level of the EC-STM signal. It can be assumed that the noise level is lower at the step bottom compared to the terrace and step top, which can be seen in the vicinity of the marked step edges or at the one marked with an arrow. b) Waterfall plot for the reaction “on” and “off” comprised of several line scans (height profile in the scan direction) across the step edges marked in a). The noise level is lower at the step bottom; an exemplary position is marked with an arrow. c) Multiple line scans for the reaction “on” stacked on top of each other. d) Comparison of the noise level for the terrace, step top, and step bottom. Data are chosen as marked in c). The histograms account for the derivatives of the height signal with respect to adjacent data points ($\delta z/\delta x$); details in the main text. A histogram of high intensity and small width corresponds to a low noise level and *vice versa*. One can deduce that step bottoms are less active than terraces and step tops.

Per each set, the n-EC-STM signal (here, the height) will be derived with respect to adjacent data points, according to the equation:

$$\left(\frac{\delta z}{\delta x}\right)_{x_1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z_2 - z_1}{x_2 - x_1} + \frac{z_1 - z_0}{x_1 - x_0} \right)$$

where (x_0, z_0) , (x_1, z_1) and (x_2, z_2) are three successive data points. Subsequently, histograms will be compiled from the signal derivatives. According to reference 47, the histograms were fitted using Gaussian curves. Both the full width at half maximum (FWHM) and the height of the Gaussians serve as a measure for the noise level. At high noise levels, the slopes between successive data points divert more from each other (due to the spikes in the signal). Consequently, the signal derivatives lead to a broad histogram. Therefore, a large FWHM and low intensity of the Gaussian fit refer to a high noise level, and *vice versa*. The fitting parameters of each histogram are given in Table S2 of the Supporting Information. In **Figure 3d**, the histograms for the reaction

“on” are given. The curves corresponding to the step top and terrace sites match each other. They can therefore be assigned a comparable activity. The histogram of the step bottom shows a narrower shape of higher intensity. Therefore, the step bottom remains relatively inactive. In the case of no ongoing surface reaction (“off”), the noise level over the surface is low and equal for all types of sites, as shown in Figure S4 of the Supporting Information.

Additional n-EC-STM measurements of Pt₅Gd are shown in the Supporting Information. As a general side note, the scan size of different EC-STM images may differ from each other. The corresponding parameters are included in Table S1 of the Supporting Information. However, note that the evaluation of the noise level is independent of these parameters, as only the noise between individual features of the same image is compared. A comparison between the noise levels, such as the FWHMs, between different n-EC-STM measurements is not feasible, as the extent of the noise would be dependent on the tip size and shape, and its insulation. Therefore, a profound comparison of local reactivity is only possible within a series of images acquired in a short time to prevent changes. Features can then be compared to *e.g.* terrace sites as a reference. In the case of Figure S5 of the Supporting Information, a concavity is captured. The respective quantification process suggests that areas close to the concave sites demonstrate less noise than adjacent convex sites. In total, on the Pt₅Gd surfaces, it can be assumed that sites of higher tentative coordination, such as step bottom sites and concavities, show inferior activity than terrace and step top sites.

Next, the results of the n-EC-STM measurements for Pt₅Pr in 0.1 M HClO₄ are presented. A typical EC-STM image is shown in **Figure 4a** with the corresponding waterfall plots in **Figure 4b**. The potential was switched from the reaction “on” to “off” conditions and back to “on” as labeled in the image. As expected, the noise level of the surface is high when the reaction is switched “on”

compared to “off”. It can be assumed that elevated positions show a higher noise level than concavities, similar to the case of Pt₅Gd. Arrows mark some recesses of lower noise levels.

Figure 4. n-EC-STM measurement results on Pt₅Pr in 0.1 M HClO₄. a) During the recording of the STM image, the sample potential was varied from the reaction “on” to “off” conditions and back to “on”, as labeled in the image. Multiple step edges are present; one of them is highlighted with a dotted line. It can be assumed that the noise level is higher at elevated spots and lower at recesses. Some of the low-noise areas are marked by arrows. b) Waterfall plot showing line scans (height profile in scan direction) across the right step edge marked in a). Near the bottom of the step, there is a gap that shows no noise, as indicated by the arrow. c) Line scans of the step edge

marked in a). The bottom of the step shows fewer noise features than the top and terraces. d) Histograms rendered from the data shown and marked in c). Step top and terraces possess a broader and low-intensity histogram compared to step bottoms. Therefore, step top and terraces contribute the most to the overall activity and to a similar extent. Step bottom sites remain relatively inactive.

The noise level over the step bottom, top, and terraces are quantified and compared according to the procedure explained above for **Figure 3**. Data sets are divided as marked in **Figure 4c**. Again, data sets for step top and bottom are sized equally for a reliable comparison. In **Figure 4d**, step top and terrace areas show a broadened and low-intensity histogram compared to the step bottom. This indicates that the former are more active than the latter. Additional measurements on concavities shown in Figure S6 confirm that areas close to the concave sites show a lower noise level and thus lower activity than adjacent convex sites.

Discussion

As mentioned in the Introduction, pure Pt binds ORR intermediates stronger than optimal. Alloying Pt increases the ORR activity since strain effects can weaken the binding energy toward chemisorbed species. However, the binding becomes “too weak” at a certain point, and thus the ORR performance diminishes again. Following a volcano-like trend, it was reported that Pt₅Gd is close to the top of the volcano on the weaker binding side, whereas Pt₅Pr binds considerably weaker.⁴² Those binding conditions can be seen as an “average” behavior of the polycrystalline surface. Still, locally, sites of certain coordination can differ from the “average” binding trend. Inspired by the study on pure Pt, one can assume that surface sites with lower coordination bind the ORR-intermediates stronger than the terraces and *vice versa*. Correspondingly, sites with higher coordination should bind weaker.^{18,19,20}

With those considerations in mind, one can explain the trends observed in the n-EC-STM measurements. On both the Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr surfaces, step bottom sites and concavities are inactive. Those sites belong to the category of “over-coordinated” sites and thus have the weakest binding energies towards the intermediates. Since “on average”, terrace sites on those Pt alloy surfaces already bind weaker than optimal, surface sites that bind even weaker show the lowest activity. Step top and terrace sites show the highest activity. Their noise levels are similar, indicating that they are comparably active. One can only speculate about the reason why terrace and step top sites show similar activities. On the one hand, the differences in binding energies between the terrace and step top sites could be less pronounced than the differences in binding energies between the terrace and step bottom sites. On the other hand, step top sites could bind much stronger than terrace sites such that they already bind “too strongly”, which would diminish their activity. In the illustrative view of a volcano plot, step top and terrace sites would then be on different sites of the top of the volcano. Nonetheless, we can state that both step top and terrace sites are beneficial for the ORR activity on both Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd.

Expanding these observations from extended surfaces to nanoparticles, one can assume that Pt₅Pr and Pt₅Gd particles, which possess terrace and “undercoordinated” sites, will show high ORR activities. This would be in line with the report of a record-high ORR performance of round, “classically”-shaped Pt₅Gd nanoparticles.³⁹ Their ORR activity (normalized to surface area) was determined to be higher than the activity of other alloys exhibiting the same round shape. The authors also compared nanoparticles of different, mass-selected sizes and within a certain size range. A trend of higher activities for larger particles is observed. The higher the size of a round

nanoparticle, the higher the share of terrace sites, which confirms the high activity of the terrace sites. Also, in line with our findings, concave and defective Pt_xPr nanoparticles as synthesized by Fichtner *et al.* showed a lower ORR activity than the extended surface.³⁶ As mentioned in the Introduction, the trends of convex nanoparticles showing a higher ORR activity are inverse to the trend for concave nanoparticles made of pure Pt which are highly active.²⁰ Thus, it is apparent that the knowledge of the active sites for a certain system is essential for rational catalyst design.

Conclusion

In summary, using electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy, the nature of active sites on Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr surfaces was *in-situ* elucidated under ORR conditions. Results showed that the sites with higher coordination, such as at the bottom of step edges or concavities, remain relatively inactive. In contrast, sites with lower coordination and terrace sites contribute the most to the overall activity. Following these observations, one can expect that nanostructured Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr electrocatalysts comprised of terraces and sites with lower coordination should reach the highest performances. Thus, classical “round” nanoparticles³⁵ can be expected to perform better than their convex and defective counterparts³⁶. Hence, the findings presented here should be useful in optimizing the electrocatalytic performance of alloyed nanostructured Pt-lanthanide materials. Furthermore, it becomes clear that insight into the nature of active sites for each individual catalyst material is vital in rational catalyst design; and there is a need for suitable surface-sensitive techniques providing access to the active sites.

Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Supporting Information. The following files are available free of charge.

Cyclic Voltammograms and Linear Potential Sweeps, XPS and XRD, Additional n-EC-STM measurements (file type, i.e., PDF)

Corresponding Authors

*Batyr Garlyyev, Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, 85748 Garching, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0002-2756-2105; Email: batyr.garlyyev@tum.de

*Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka, Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, 85748 Garching, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0002-5970-4315; Email: bandarenka@ph.tum.de

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. ‡R.M.K. and E.P. contributed equally.

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Revealing the Nature of Active Sites on Pt-Gd and Pt-Pr Alloys during the Oxygen Reduction Reaction

Regina M. Kluge,^{1,‡} Eleftherios Psaltis,^{1,‡} Richard W. Haid,¹ Shujin Hou,^{1,2} Thorsten O.

Schmidt,¹ Oliver Schneider,³ Batyr Garlyyev,^{,1} Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka^{*,1,2}*

- 1 Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, James-Franck-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany.
- 2 Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany.
- 3 Institut für Informatik VI, Technische Universität München, Schleißheimerstraße 90a, 85748 Garching, Germany.

Contents

1. Cyclic Voltammograms and Linear Potential Sweeps.....	2
2. Compositional and structural investigation by XPS and XRD.....	3
3. Fitting parameters of the n-EC-STM measurements	4
4. Additional n-EC-STM measurements.....	5
5. References.....	8

1. Cyclic Voltammograms and Linear Potential Sweeps

Figure S1. Typical CVs of Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr electrodes. CVs are performed in Ar-saturated (Argon 5.0, Westfalen, Germany) 0.1 M HClO₄. The scan rate was 50 mV s⁻¹. The CVs are in accordance with the literature.^{1,2}

Figure S2. Linear potential sweeps recorded in the EC-STM set-up *versus* a Pt-quasi reference and exposed to air. A potential of 0 mV_{Pt} was chosen as ORR “off” for all systems. The potentials applied for ORR “on” are given in Table S1 for each n-EC-STM image.

Table S1. Experimental parameters of each n-EC-STM image presented in the main text and Supporting Information.

	potential “on” (mV _{Pt})	tip potential (mV _{Pt})	current set- point (nA)	scan size (nm ²)	scan speed (Hz)
Figure 3	-400	-50	1.0	50 x 50	1.5
Figure S4					
Figure S5	-400	-50	1.0	50 x 50	1.5
Figure 4	-400	-50	2.5	250 x 200	1.0
Figure S6	<i>cf.</i> image	-50	2.0	100 x 100	1.5

2. Compositional and structural investigation by XPS and XRD

Each XPS spectrum was fitted using the commercial CasaXPS software and a Shirley background. The fits lead to a 3.2 at% Pr and ~ 0 at% for Gd. Both suggest a completely de-alloyed surface. Detailed XRD analysis of the Pt₅Pr electrode is given in reference 1. The obtained XRD patterns of the Pt₅Gd electrode are given in Figure S3c, and the results are in accordance with the literature.^{1,2}

Figure S3. a,b) XPS and c,d) XRD data of both Pt₅Gd and Pt₅Pr crystals. From the low XPS signal of both lanthanide species, we can deduce a de-alloyed Pt surface. From the XRD spectrum, we can observe a polycrystalline nature of both samples.

3. Fitting parameters of the n-EC-STM measurements

Table S2. Parameters obtained in the fits of the histograms of all n-EC-STM images presented in the main text and Supporting Information. Symbols refer to ● – terrace site, ▲ – step top, and ▼ – step bottom.

		FWHM	FWHM	height	height	reduced chi- square	r-square
		value	error	value	error		
Figure 3							
on	●	1.0	0.055	0.30	0.014	2.5E-04	0.95
	▲	1.8	0.107	0.15	0.008	1.2E-04	0.92
	▼	1.5	0.094	0.15	0.008	1.1E-04	0.92
Figure S4							
off	●	0.70	0.037	0.18	0.0082	1.3E-04	0.95
	▲	0.70	0.037	0.19	0.0083	1.2E-04	0.96
	▼	0.67	0.033	0.20	0.0081	1.1E-04	0.96
Figure S5b							
	●	1.2	0.053	0.50	0.018	2.3E-04	0.99
	▲	1.1	0.058	0.45	0.020	3.7E-04	0.98
	▼	1.3	0.030	0.51	0.012	1.2E-04	1.00
Figure S5d							
	▼	1.8	0.053	0.37	0.0091	8.8E-05	0.99
	▲	1.8	0.061	0.32	0.0092	9.3E-05	0.99
Figure 4							
	●	1.50	0.11	0.24	0.01	2.2E-04	0.97
	▲	1.25	0.11	0.25	0.02	3.4E-04	0.95
	▼	0.86	0.09	0.34	0.03	7.5E-04	0.93

		FWHM	FWHM	height	height	reduced chi- square	r-square
Figure S6							
-100 mV _{Pt}	▼	0.88	0.20	0.32	0.060	4.4E-03	0.74
	▲	0.83	0.05	0.35	0.017	3.1E-04	0.98
-200 mV _{Pt}	▼	0.98	0.15	0.26	0.031	1.0E-03	0.88
	▲	1.03	0.08	0.28	0.018	4.3E-04	0.95
-300 mV _{Pt}	▼	0.95	0.09	0.29	0.022	6.1E-04	0.92
	▲	0.94	0.07	0.20	0.012	1.7E-04	0.94
-400 mV _{Pt}	▼	0.72	0.02	0.45	0.014	1.8E-04	0.99
	▲	0.91	0.06	0.21	0.011	1.4E-04	0.95

4. Additional n-EC-STM measurements

Pt₅Gd in 0.1 M HClO₄

Figure S4. ORR “off” of Pt₅Gd in 0.1 M HClO₄. a) The line scans are extracted from Figure 3 of the main text and stacked on top of each other. b) Histograms are divided into the terrace, step top, and step bottom as indicated in a) and at the same positions as a reaction “on” in Figure 3c. The histograms presented here for reaction “off” are narrower and of smaller width. Besides, they do not depend on the geometry of the surface site.

Figure S5. Additional n-EC-STM measurement on Pt₅Gd in 0.1 M HClO₄. a) The n-EC-STM image contains two steps, which are highlighted by grey dotted lines and are evaluated in the respective sub-images. It seems that elevated positions show more noise than lower parts of the surface. b) Linescans across the step on the left in a). The step bottom shows a lower noise level than the parts of the surface to its left and right. c) Histograms of b), confirming that step bottoms exhibit less noise. d) Line scans across the step on the right in a). e) Histogram of d). Again, the step bottom is less active than the step top.

Figure S6. Additional n-EC-STM measurement on Pt₅Pr in 0.1 M HClO₄. For each applied potential, the line scans were extracted from the n-EC-STM image and stacked on top of each other. On the right, the histograms calculated from the data plotted in the respective left images are shown for step bottom and top sites.

5. References

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